

Knowledge and Attitude of Middle-Age Population towards predisposing factors of Hypertension

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Abstract:

Background: Hypertension is one of the most common diseases affecting middle aged population of the world. It is a "Silent killer" as it is rarely symptomatic

Materials & Methods: An interview based cross-sectional study was conducted during 3 months period on a random sample of 323 individuals attending the Out Patient Department of Medicine at Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi which is one of the largest Tertiary Care Hospital in Punjab providing health care facilities to a major population of Rawalpindi and nearby areas. A sample size of 323 was calculated using WHO sample size calculator. Normotensive and Middle-aged (WHO verified: 40-60 years) individuals were selected by simple random sampling and interviewed during OPD timings. A self-structured questionnaire was used. The questions pertaining to risk factors, complications and presenting complaints were of multiple response type. Data were entered and analysed on SPSS v 23. Percentages and frequencies were calculated for categorical data.

Results: 236 (88.1%) participants considered hypertension as a disease whereas 232 (86.6%) participants thought that blood pressure monitoring was crucial. 160 (59.7%) participants did not know how to read blood pressure reading while 108 (40.3%) participants knew about it. 121 (45.1%) participants had no knowledge about normal reading of blood pressure. 32 (11.9%) participants considered 100/60-110/70 mmHg, 98 (36.6%) considered 120/80-130/90 mmHg and 17 (6.3%) considered 140/100-150/110 mmHg as normal range for blood pressure.

Conclusion: Knowledge of middle aged normotensive individuals regarding hypertension is just borderline.

Keywords: Knowledge; Attitude; Predisposing Factors; Hypertension

Introduction

Hypertension is one of the commonest diseases affecting middle aged men and women in developing and developed countries worldwide. It is a silent killer that rarely manifests symptoms.¹ Risk factors for hypertension can be categorized as modifiable and non-modifiable. Modifiable risk factors include smoking, dietary habits, obesity, sedentary lifestyle and stress. Non modifiable include age, gender and genetic predisposition.² Increasing public awareness to the disease, its risk factors, ominous outcomes and requirement of life-long treatment warrants early detection for better prognosis.¹

In 2008, approximately 40% adult population aged 25 and above had been diagnosed with hypertension worldwide. In African population, the prevalence of hypertension is 46% in the age group of 25 years and above while amongst American population it is 35% in the same age group.¹ In 2016, 75 million Americans (29%) suffered from hypertension. Awareness towards hypertension among US citizens is quite high which is around 72%.³

In 2013, prevalence of hypertension in India was 29.8% and in China 26.6%.^{5,6} In 2010, the National Health Survey of Pakistan (NHSP) estimated that hypertension affected 18% of adults above 18 years of age and 33% of adults beyond 45 years of age.⁴ The 1990-1994 survey of NHSP observed that 70% of hypertensive population in Pakistan were unaware of their disease.⁷ According to a study conducted in Karachi in 2002, the Mean Awareness Score of hypertensive participants was 19.6 whereas the score was 16.3 in normotensive participants.⁸ At present, it is estimated that about 1 billion people worldwide have hypertension (BP>140/90 mmHg), and this number is expected to increase to 1.56 billion by 2025.⁹ Hypertension is becoming a bigger contributor to morbidity and mortality in Pakistan which emphasizes the need to work out comprehensive strategy to bring awareness in masses regarding risk factors of hypertension for controlling the disease and preventing its complications. It is well known that awareness aids in early detection, motivation for self-

care and compliance to treatment. It would be achieved through incorporating healthy behaviour and positive attitude for better control of the disease.

The objective of this study was to assess the level of knowledge and attitude among middle aged population towards predisposing factors of hypertension in patients attending Out Patient Department of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi

Materials and Methods:

An interview based cross-sectional study was conducted during 3 months period on a random sample of 323 individuals attending the Out Patient Department of Medicine at Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi which is one of the largest Tertiary Care Hospital in Punjab providing health care facilities to a major population of Rawalpindi and nearby areas.

A sample size of 323 was calculated keeping precision at 5% and confidence interval at 95% [8]. Normotensive and Middle-aged (WHO verified: 40-60 years) individuals were selected by simple random sampling and interviewed during OPD timings (9 a.m. to 2 p.m.). A self-structured questionnaire consisting majorly of close ended questions with “yes” and “no” options was used to assess the knowledge and attitude of participants towards risk factors and complications of hypertension. The first part of the questionnaire dealt with the demographic details of participants. Second part dealt with the participants’ perception regarding hypertension as a disease. Third part had questions pertaining to awareness about risk factors, complications and presenting complaints of hypertension. Last part of questionnaire dealt with attitude of the participants regarding prevention, control and treatment of hypertension. The questions pertaining to risk factors, complications and presenting complaints were of multiple response type. Verbal informed consent was taken from all participants and they were informed about the objectives of study before interview and confidentiality was maintained.

Data was entered and analysed on SPSS v 23. Percentages and frequencies were calculated for categorical data.

Results:

The mean age was 47.47±6.7 years and gender distribution was male 35.6% and female 64.4% (Table I).

Table I: Demographic profile of the Participants (N=323)

VARIABLES		N (%)*
Age	Mean=47.51±6.8	
Gender	Male	115 (35.6)
	Female	208 (64.4)
Education	Uneducated	114 (35.3)
	Primary	53 (16.4)
	Middle	33 (10.2)
	Matric	95 (29.4)
	Graduate	28 (8.7)

*N= number, %= Percentage

The total number of participants was 323 out of which 268 (83%) participants had heard about hypertension whereas as 55 (17%) participants did not know about hypertension. They were not asked further questions (Table II).

Table II: Perception of hypertension as a disease; awareness regarding its risk factors, presenting complaints, complications and attitude of the participants towards its prevention, control and treatment

	N (%)*
Heard about Hypertension	268 (83%)
1. Perception	
Consider Hypertension a disease	236 (88.1%)
2. Awareness	
Predisposition to hypertension due to positive family history	189 (70%)
Complications	
Heart disease	128 (67.7%)
Stroke/Hemiplegia	155 (82%)
Loss of vision	50 (26.5%)
Kidney disease	56 (29.6%)
Risk Factors	
Obesity	174 (68%)
Smoking a pack of cigarette daily	148 (57.8%)
High fat diet	210 (82%)
Sedentary lifestyle	141 (55.1%)
High salt intake	226 (88.3%)
Diabetes mellitus	135 (52.7%)
Old age	135 (52.7%)
Stress	213 (83.2%)
Food predisposing to Hypertension	
Oily food	223 (92.1%)
Fruit and vegetables	20 (8.3%)
Beef, mutton, chicken	158 (65.3%)

Fast food	193 (79.8%)
Presenting Symptoms	
Severe headache	174 (66.2%)
Fatigue/confusion	109 (41.4%)
Vision problem	36 (13.7%)
Chest pain	22 (8.4%)
Difficulty in breathing	34 (12.9%)
Irregular heartbeat	53 (20.2%)
Blood in urine	6 (2.3%)
Pounding in chest, neck or ears	33 (12.5%)
3. Attitude	
BP Checking	
Daily	11 (4.1%)
Weekly	44 (16.4%)
Monthly	37 (13.8%)
Yearly	5 (1.9%)
Occasionally	124 (46.3%)
Never	47 (17.5%)
Consult a doctor in case of raised blood pressure	261 (97.8%)
Exercise	
No exercise	186 (69.4%)
Daily exercise	82 (30.6%)

*N= Number, %= Percentage

236 (88.1%) participants considered hypertension as a disease whereas 232 (86.6%) participants thought that blood pressure monitoring was crucial. 160 (59.7%) participants did not know how to read blood pressure reading while 108 (40.3%) participants knew about it. 121 (45.1%) participants had no knowledge about normal reading of blood pressure. 32 (11.9%) participants considered 100/60-110/70 mmHg, 98 (36.6%) considered 120/80-130/90 mmHg and 17 (6.3%) considered 140/100-150/110 mmHg as normal range for blood pressure.

140 (52.2%) participants had positive family history for hypertension and out of them 189 (70%) participants reckoned it as a predisposing factor for hypertension. 190 (70.9%) participants believed that hypertension can lead to complications.

Most of the participants (>65%) were aware of stroke and heart diseases as the major complications of hypertension. >65% of the participants marked the increased salt intake, stress, high fat diet and obesity as risk factors of hypertension. 92% of the participants believed that excessive consumption of oily food could lead to hypertension. 23.6% of the participants had no knowledge regarding presenting symptoms of hypertension whereas majority of the participants were aware of headache and fatigue as common presenting symptoms of hypertension.

191 (71.3%) participants believed that hypertension was a non-communicable disease. 255 (95.1%) participants were of the view that prevention helps in controlling hypertension. 247 (92.2%) participants believed that treatment of hypertension was possible. 57.5% participants were of the opinion that short term therapy can treat hypertension whereas 42.5% considered that life-long treatment was required. 206 (77.2%) participants believed that hypertension was a curable disease.

124 (46.3%) participants got their blood pressure checked occasionally whereas 47 (17.5%) participants never got their blood pressure checked. 261 (97.8%) participants said that they would consult a doctor in case of high blood pressure. 233 (86.9%) participants believed that daily exercise helped in preventing hypertension whereas 186 (69.4%) participants did not have the habit of doing daily exercise.

Discussion:

Hypertension is one of the major cardiovascular diseases and its prevalence is increasing rapidly in developing countries of Asia.^{10,11} Hypertension itself is a major risk factor for stroke and ischemic heart disease.^{11,12} Its high prevalence has enhanced morbidity which has increased the cost of treatment and has over-burdened the country's economy and health care system.¹³ Hence it is important to take measures to reduce its incidence by increasing awareness among general population regarding hypertension, its risk factors and complications. Better understanding of disease will help people in changing their behaviour regarding modifiable risk factors to make its prevention easier to achieve.¹⁴

We studied normotensive and middle-aged population to assess their knowledge about hypertension, its risk factors, complications and symptoms. It was based upon the proposition that developing a healthy lifestyle and modifying notorious behaviour early in life can prevent the development of hypertension and decrease its incidence.

Education plays a principle role in developing healthy behaviour and lifestyle. Pakistan is a developing country with a literacy rate of 58% (74% in urban areas and 49% in rural areas).¹⁵ Our study showed a proportional relationship between educational status and awareness level of participants regarding hypertension. 35.3% of the participants were uneducated and hence, they had scarce knowledge about risk factors, complications and presenting symptoms of hypertension.

Majority of the participants had heard about hypertension and considered it a disease. Most of the participants (>65%) reckoned positive family history of hypertension as predictor of this disease. It was reassuring that obesity, high salt intake, high fat diet and stress were considered risk factors for hypertension by most of the participants. A large majority understands that consuming oily foods can lead to hypertension similar to the findings of a study conducted in Karachi during 2008.⁸ Participants were not aware of smoking, sedentary lifestyle and uncontrolled diabetes mellitus as important risk factors for hypertension. In Pakistan the prevalence of cigarette smoking among males is 36% and among females is 9%.^{16,17} A quarter of population in Pakistan is overweight and obese with 25% prevalence for obesity.¹⁸ According to a review article published in December 2016, the current prevalence of diabetes mellitus in Pakistan was 11.77%.¹⁹ It revealed that modifiable risk factors were becoming prevalent in our society hence knowledge about these factors was crucial in prevention of the disease.

More than 65% of the participants recognized stroke and heart disease as the major complications of hypertension but many did not know that eye and kidney disease were also its complications. A study conducted in Karachi corroborates our findings.⁸ This low level of awareness regarding complications demands education of the masses in order to prevent complications. Prevention of any chronic disease can be achieved when individuals take full responsibility of their own health. Hence, awareness regarding seriousness of risk factors and complications of hypertension will help the individual to incline towards health caring attitude.

It is evident from table 2 that headache and fatigue were attributed to hypertension. Study conducted by Zafar SN et al suggests similar results.⁸ Participants were not aware of chest pain, vision problems, difficulty in breathing, irregular heartbeat, blood in urine and pounding in chest, neck or ears as presenting symptoms of hypertension.

A significant percentage of the participants get their blood pressure checked occasionally and agreed upon consulting a doctor in case of raised blood pressure. However data revealed that majority of the participants got their blood pressure checked only in the hour of need.

Higher percentage of the participants believed that hypertension was a non-communicable disease and its treatment was possible. It was interesting to note that a large proportion of them believed that hypertension

was curable with short term which is a common misconception in our country. Attitude towards treatment is particularly important in the outcome of disease and development of its complications. Correct knowledge will create a positive and self-caring attitude which will motivate people to adopt healthy habits. Majority of the participants believed that prevention can help control hypertension. In addition, a large proportion of participants did believe that daily exercise could help in controlling blood pressure but most of the participants were not in the practice of daily exercise. When asked about the reason, majority of them remarked that following mundane tasks of everyday life is contemplated as physical activity.

Conclusion:

Knowledge of middle aged normotensive individuals regarding hypertension is just borderline. People do not have comprehensive understanding for adopting healthy approach and its advantages for their health and fitness. Therefore, it is imperative to start health education and awareness programs throughout the country.

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